

Research Article

Comparative Analysis of Two Formulated Poly Herbal Foot Cream for Cracked Heels

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ABSTRACT

Herbal crack heel cream is a natural cream, that is made from various plants and plant products. They have various properties including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, hydrating and wound healing properties. Different plants were used like *Curcuma longa*, *Carica papaya* and *Aloe barbedensis* since the formulation's goal was to give heels for both protection and smoothness as well as it prevents diabetic foot ulcer. The materials and methods used for the extraction of the plant and plant products for the formulation and evaluation of poly herbal foot crack cream includes organoleptic evaluation (colour, odour and appearance) and physico-chemical evaluation like pH, moisture absorption test, viscosity, irritancy, spreadability, washability, smear test, homogeneity and stability testing (for 30 days) were observed. Different evaluation parameters were used like pH, moisture absorption test, viscosity, irritancy, spreadability, smear test, homogeneity and stability testing (for 30 days) which were shown in the evaluations table in the manuscript. The herbal foot crack creams have a smooth and greasy textures, aromatic odour and have dark olive green and yellowish orange colour. The different plant and plant products used were turmeric, aloe vera pulp, papaya leaves and papaya pulp for the formulation of foot crack creams. Comparing both the creams formulation-I was found to be more efficient which requires further investigation of its in-vivo and in-vitro evaluations.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian traditional Ayurvedic system of medicine is a holistic approach that focuses on the use of natural products to promote health and

balance in the body by removing toxins, reducing symptoms and increasing disease resistance. In Ayurveda the use of herbal formulations is emphasized as it not only alleviates the disease but also stops it from reoccurring. According to World

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Health Organization (WHO), around 80% of people around the world are still dependent on the use of natural herbal products for the maintenance of a healthy living. These natural products are either used alone or are used together with other herbs. The latter, referred to as "Polyherbal Formulations," has recently garnered remarkable attention. The idea of "Polyherbalism" was promoted in Ayurvedic literature such as the Sarangdhar Samhita' because occasionally a single herb is unable to achieve the intended health benefits. The literature also suggests that mixture of various herbs in an appropriate ratio improves therapeutic efficacy and decreases the noxious effects. Thus, the term "Poly herbal Formulations" refers to those pharmaceutical preparation that incorporates multiple herbs to maximize the curative effect and reduces the noxious effect of the herbs [1]. Foot creams containing poly herbal extracts are now preferred over allopathic medicines which contain synthetic chemicals as they do not focus on holistic treatment of the disease [2]. Poly herbal formulations are comparatively safer as they rarely produce any serious adverse effects like hypersensitivity reactions. The main aim of the formulation was to provide protection as well as moisture and softness to the heels hence *Carica papaya*, *Curcuma longa* and *Aloe barbadensis* were chosen as it shows anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-fungal and anti-oxidant property [3].

Aim

Aim: To prepare and evaluate herbal foot crack cream

Objective:

- To prepare the extract of *Curcuma longa*, *Carica papaya* and *Aloe barbadensis*.
- Formulation of two herbal foot crack cream by using poly herbal plant extract.

- Evaluation and comparison of two formulated herbal foot crack cream with the help of different organoleptic and physico-chemical parameters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

FORMULATION-

Plant collection

Collection of Turmeric

The rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* were collected from Majhitar, East Sikkim, India after that the rhizomes were shade dried and coarsely powdered using mortar and pestle.

Fig.1: Turmeric powder

Collection of Papaya

The leaves of *Carica papaya* were collected from Bardang, East Sikkim, India after that the leaves were shade dried and coarsely powdered using mortar and pestle.

Fig.2: Papaya leaves powder

Collection of Aloe vera

The fresh leaves of *Aloe barbadensis* were collected from Gangtok, Sikkim, India after that the fresh leaves were cut into small pieces and scraped with the help of spatula after keeping it vertically against the beaker so that the toxic latex is removed so that it does not cause skin irritation [4].

Fig.3: Fresh leaves of aloe vera

Chemicals

These include beeswax, borax, methyl paraben, coconut oil, Vitamin E capsule, camphor and petroleum jelly.

Extraction

Curcuma longa rhizome and *Carica papaya* leaf were collected, shade dried and powdered. The extraction of *Carica papaya* and *Curcuma longa* was done by using ethanol [5] while *Aloe barbadensis* pulp was scraped out manually after keeping it vertically against the beaker to remove latex from the leaves as it causes skin irritation. The above stated powders were taken in separate beakers and extracted with ethanol for 72 hours with occasional agitation and then filtered.

Fig.4: Dried rhizomes of turmeric

Extraction of *Curcuma longa*

1. Fresh rhizomes were collected and shade dried for 10 days [9].
2. The dried rhizomes were then powdered using motor and pestle.
3. The powdered rhizomes weighed 26.18g and then it was macerated in a beaker using 224ml of ethanol.
4. The prepared mixture was covered with aluminium foil and was allowed to macerate for 3 days (72 hours) with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered using filter paper and muslin cloth.
5. The solvent in the filtrate was then removed by using rotary vacuum evaporator. The filtrate obtained in the china dish was further dried on water bath to obtain a semi solid mass [6].
6. After drying the extract was cooled, weighed and stored by covering with aluminium foil.

Fig.5: Filtration of turmeric

Extraction of *Carica papaya*

1. Fresh papaya leaves were collected and shade dried for 10 days.
2. The dried leaves were then powdered using motor and pestle.
3. The leaves weighed 39.67g and then it was macerated in a beaker using 330ml of ethanol.

4. The prepared mixture was covered with aluminium foil and was allowed to macerate for 3 days with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered using filter paper and muslin cloth.
5. The solvent in the filtrate was then removed by using rotary vacuum evaporator. The filtrate obtained in the china dish was further dried on water bath to obtain a semi solid mass [7].
6. After drying the extract was cooled, weighed and stored by covering with aluminium foil.

Fig 6: Dried leaves of papaya shade dried

Fig 7: Heating papaya extract on water bath

Collection of Aloe vera pulp

1. Fresh leaves of aloe vera were kept vertically against the beaker for 4-5 hrs.
2. After the toxic latex was removed the leaves were cut and the aloe vera pulp was scrapped out using scalpel.

Preparation of Formulation-I

Water phase containing borax, rose water, vitamin E, camphor, extracts and pulp were taken separately in a china dish and oil phase containing coconut oil, bees wax, petroleum jelly were taken in a separate china dish and melted on hot water bath maintaining the temperature of 70°C with proper mixing [11]. Remove the oil phase from the water bath and add previously prepared water phase to oil phase while it is still hot and stir continuously with glass rod [13]. Lastly add methyl paraben and then again mix properly slowly when the temperature drops the formulation will become viscous.

Preparation of aqueous phase

In a clean china dish take all the water phases like borax(3.52g), rose water(23.6ml), vitamin E(2 capsules), camphor(QS), total extract of *Curcuma longa* and *Carica papaya*(7.41g) and *Aloe barbadensis* pulp(2.87g) on water bath maintaining the temperature of 70°C.

Preparation of oil phase

In a separate china dish take all the oil phases like coconut oil(40ml), bees wax(12.8g) and petroleum jelly(QS) and mix properly maintaining the temperature of 70°C.

Mixing of both phases and Formulation of w/o type of foot crack cream

Remove the oil phase from the water bath and add previously prepared water phase to oil phase in hot condition and stir continuously with glass rod. Lastly add methyl paraben(10.08g) and then again mix properly, slowly when the temperature drops the formulation will become viscous.

Table No.1: Ingredients used in herbal foot crack cream for formulation I

Sr.No	Ingredients	Quantity	Use
1	Bees wax	12.8g	Emulsifying agent and thickener
2	Borax	3.52g	Emulsifying agent and preservative
3	Methyl Paraben	10.08g	Preservative
4	Coconut oil	40ml	Moisturiser and emollient
5	Rose water	23.6ml	Cleanser and toner
6	Turmeric extract	1.71g	Anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory and colorant
7	Papaya leaf extract	5.43g	Wound healing
8	Aloe vera extract	2.87g	Emollient, moisturiser and wound healing

FORMULATION-II

Plant Collection

Collection of Turmeric

The rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* was collected from Majhitar, East Sikkim, India after that the rhizomes were shade dried and coarsely powdered using mortar and pestle [8].

Fig 8: Dried rhizome of turmeric

Collection of Papaya

Carica papaya was collected from Majhitar, East Sikkim, India after that the fruit was cut into small pieces and the fresh pulp was carved out and collected.

Collection of Aloe Vera

The fresh leaves of *Aloe barbadensis* were collected from Gangtok, Sikkim, India after that the fresh pulp of *Aloe barbadensis* was scraped out

after the leaf was kept vertically against the beaker to remove latex from the leaves as it causes skin irritation.

Fig 9: Fresh Aloe vera gel scraped out

Chemicals

These include beeswax, borax, methylparaben, coconut oil, vitamin E capsule, camphor and petroleum jelly.

Extraction

Curcuma longa rhizome and *Carica papaya* leaf were collected, shade dried and powdered. The extraction of *Carica papaya* and *Curcuma longa* was done by using ethanol while *Aloe barbadensis* pulp was scraped out manually after keeping it vertically against the beaker to remove latex from the leaves as it causes skin irritation. The above stated powders were taken in separate beakers and extracted with ethanol for 72 hours with occasional agitation and then filtered.

Extraction of *Curcuma longa*

1. Fresh rhizomes were collected and shade dried for 10 days [12].
2. The dried rhizomes were then powdered using mortar and pestle.
3. The powdered rhizomes weighed 26.18g and then it was macerated in a beaker using 224ml of ethanol.
4. The prepared mixture was covered with aluminium foil and was allowed to macerate for 3 days (72 hours) with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered using filter paper and muslin cloth.
5. The solvent in the filtrate was then removed by using rotary vacuum evaporator. The filtrate obtained in the china dish was further dried on water bath to obtain a semi solid mass [14].
6. After drying the extract was cooled, weighed and stored by covering with aluminium foil [10].

Fig.10: Dried rhizomes of turmeric

Fig 11: Rotary vacuum evaporator

Collection of *Carica papaya* pulp

1. Ripe papaya fruit was cut and the pulp was scrapped out using a scalpel.
2. By using mortar and pestle the pulp was crushed to form a fine paste.

Collection of *Aloe vera* pulp

1. Fresh leaves of aloe vera were kept vertically against the beaker for 4-5 hrs.
2. After the toxic latex was removed the leaves were cut and the aloe vera pulp was scrapped out using scalpel.

Preparation of Formulation-II

Water phase containing borax, rose water, vitamin E, camphor, extracts and pulp were taken separately in a china dish and oil phase containing coconut oil, bees wax, petroleum jelly were taken in a separate china dish and melted on hot water bath maintaining the temperature of 70°C with proper mixing [11]. Remove the oil phase from the water bath and add previously prepared water phase to oil phase while it is still hot and stir continuously with glass rod [13]. Lastly add methyl paraben and then again mix properly slowly when the temperature drops the formulation will become viscous.

Preparation of aqueous phase

In a clean china dish take all the water phases like borax(3.52g), rose water(23.6ml), vitamin E(2 capsules), camphor(QS), extract(1.71g) and pulp(8.3g) on water bath maintaining the temperature of 70°C.

Preparation of oil phase

In a separate china dish take all the oil phases like coconut oil(40ml), bees wax(12.8g) and petroleum

jelly(QS) as per the mentioned quantity and mix properly maintaining the temperature of 70°C.

Mixing of both phases and Formulation of w/o type of foot crack cream

Remove the oil phase from the water bath and add previously prepared water phase to oil phase in hot condition and stir continuously with glass rod. Lastly add methyl paraben(10.08g) and then again mix properly, slowly when the temperature drops the formulation will become viscous.

Table No.2: Ingredients used in herbal foot crack cream for formulation II

SL.No	Ingredients	Quantity	Uses
1	Bees wax	12.8g	Emulsifying agent and thickener
2	Borax	3.52g	Emulsifying agent and preservative
3	Methyl Paraben	10.08g	Preservative
4	Coconut oil	40ml	Moisturiser and emollient
5	Rose water	23.6ml	Cleanser and toner
6	Turmeric extract	1.71g	Anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory and colorant
7	Papaya pulp extract	5.43g	Wound healing
8	Aloe vera extract	2.87g	Emollient, moisturiser and wound healing

Evaluation Parameters (Formulation I and II):

Organoleptic Evaluation

For this the colour, odour, texture and appearance of both the herbal foot crack cream was observed and evaluated [16].

Physico-chemical Evaluation

pH

About 1gm of each cream was weighed and dissolved in 10 ml ethanol by it heating on water bath. The content was filtered and pH was measured using pH meter.

Fig.12: pH test

Moisture absorption test

100ml water was taken in a beaker and placed in desiccators and allowed to get saturated. 10 mg both crack cream were taken in a watch glass and was placed in the desiccators for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs moisture absorption was noted [17].

Fig.13: Moisture Absorption test

Viscosity

Both the sample were taken in a beaker and was allowed to rotate at 100 rpm using spindle number 64 in Brookfield viscometer. Average of three reading was taken.

Fig.14: Viscosity

Irritancy

An area on the dorsal surface of the hand was marked. Both the cream was applied to the specified area and the time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, oedema was checked for regular intervals up to 24 hours and reported. This test was conducted after taking permission from the volunteer.

Fig 15: Test for irritancy

Spreadability

Spreadability was determined by taking 0.5gm of each cream on the glass slide over 1cm of diameter. Second slide was placed over it. Weight of 100gm was placed on it for 5 minutes [18]. The increase in the diameter of the cream was noted. Following formula was used to calculate the spreadability

$$S = m \cdot \frac{L}{T}$$

Where,

S = spreadability

m = weight of the upper glass slide

L = length moved on the glass side

T = time taken

Fig 16: Spreadability test

Washability

Little amount of cream was applied over the skin and then was washed under water.

Fig.17: Washability test

Smear test

Some amount of both the creams was applied on the skin and the type of smear formed was checked [19].

Fig 18: Smear test

Homogeneity

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and test.

Stability testing

Stability study was done for 30 days and it has been observed that the prepared polyherbal foot crack creams were stable for one month with respect to appearance, color, odour, pH, moisture absorption test, viscosity, irritancy, spreadability, washability, smear test, homogeneity [20].

Fig 19: pH test after stability testing for 30 days

RESULTS:

Table No.3: Observation table on Extractive values

Sl. No.	Plant extracts	Extractive value
1.	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	2.48%
2.	<i>Carica papaya</i>	5.92%

Table No.4: Observation Table on evaluation Parameters

SL.NO	PARAMETERS	Formulation-I	Formulation-II	Standard value [15],[22]
1	Colour, odour and appearance	Dark olive green, aromatic and greasy	Yellowish orange, Aromatic and greasy	Appealing
2	pH	6.11	4.6	4.0-7.0
3	Moisture absorption test	0%	0%	0%
4	Viscosity(100 rpm)	5771 cP	2723 cP	1100-40000 cP
5	Irritancy	No irritancy	No irritancy	No irritancy
6	Spreadability	Good(29.44gm.cm/s)	Good(26.455gm.cm/s)	Good
7	Washability	Washable	Washable	Washable
8	Smear test	Greasy	Greasy	Greasy
9	Homogeneity	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous

Table No. 5: Stability testing

Time period	Formulation-I(after 30 days)	Formulation-II(after 30 days)
Appearance	No microbial or fungal growth	No microbial or fungal growth
Colour	No colour change	No colour change
Odour	No bad odour	No bad odour
Consistency	No aggregates	No aggregates
pH	No change	No change

DISCUSSION

The created herbal foot crack cream have a smooth and greasy texture, a pleasant aroma, and a dark olive green colour. The herbal foot crack cream's

physical and chemical characteristics were meticulously extracted and it's pH was checked which was found to be 6.11 and 4.6 for formulation I and II respectively, which is within the optimal range. The moisture absorption was measured and

the percentage obtained was 0% for both the formulations. The viscosity of the crack cream was found to be 5771 cP and 2723 cP for formulation I and II respectively. The skin irritation test was conducted and was found to be negative (no irritation) for both the formulation. Further spreadability test was done which was found to be good as 29.44gm.cm/s for formulation I and for formulation II it was found to be 26.455gm.cm/s. The washability for both the crack cream was checked which was easily washable. The smear formed during the smear test was found to be greasy for both of them. Both the formulations were found to be homogenous during its homogeneity test.

CONCLUSION

The plants *Curcuma longa*, *Carica papaya* and *Aloe barbadensis* underwent a series of evaluation test following their ethanol extraction. The produced compound was tested well, yielding favourable findings multiple times. A small group of volunteers has used this cream and found it to be skin friendly which indicated that the cream does not irritate the skin. Furthermore, the produced cream was standardized through evaluation of various physical and chemical attributes including pH, appearance, order, viscosity where the product demonstrates acceptable outcomes. We can conclude that formulation I is more preferable than formulation II because of its better consistency and moisturising property. Further research related to different phytoconstituents were required and along with *in-vivo* and *in-vitro* model studies needs to be performed for further establishment.

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Writing, visualization and editing. R.D: Reviewing, conceptualization, editing, visualization and validation. All authors reviewed properly and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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